

GASTRONOMY TOURISM IN MODERN WORLD

¹Akhrorova Nargiza, ²Saidova Amina

¹Lecturer in “Silk Road” International University of Tourism and Cultural Heritage, ²Student in “Silk Road” International University of Tourism and Cultural Heritage

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11217848>

Abstract. *This study aims to explore the development and importance of gastronomic tourism these days. Since, food considers to be an integral part of the tourism itself, that is to say food plays a significant role in our lives. Gastronomic tourism offers also huge opportunities for communities in order to integrate local food systems, so it considers to be part of our lives. Nowadays, also a great many of people travel around not only with the purpose to see stunning views of the nature and mondo-fabulous venues of the world with their eyes, but also to taste lip-smacking foods of various cuisine kitchens. It is not a secret that each kitchen is different and unique with its flavors and foods. Food tourism, culinary tourism, and gastronomy tourism has a similar purpose and they have been developed and tried to do their best over the years. Beverages and food are consuming needs of people's everyday lives. This study will also explore about the venues, the center of gastronomic hub, as well as the place and time of its start, and who was the first person who actually took an engaging interest in gastronomic tourism. Besides it, it will explore about our cuisine kitchen which is liked not only by our local people, but also by tourists, and also it will emphasize about its uniqueness, and scrumptious foods and especially our Uzbek bread where it cannot be found anywhere. Also, the present study is examination of Mexico's kitchen, its flavors and uniqueness, and it will emphasize why Mexican kitchen is liked by a great many of people. That is to say, it will cover the uniqueness of Mexico's kitchen, and some of its national foods that are liked by tourists. Unfortunately, in comparison to Mexico our country is logging behind, but the ways how to develop our Uzbek kitchen will be analyzed in this work. People live in the era of globalization, so there are lots of various ways how to make gastronomic tourism more engaging and how develop the menus of Uzbekistan and Mexico's kitchens, in order to attract more tourists, so this article is will be analyzed about it.*

Key words: *gastronomy Tourism, cuisine kitchen, lip-smacking foods, restaurants.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu tadqiqot bugungi kunda gastronomik turizmning rivojlanishi va ahamiyatini o'rganishga qaratilgan. Chunki oziq-ovqat turizmning ajralmas qismi hisoblanadi, ya'ni oziq-ovqat bizning hayotimizda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Gastronomik turizm mahalliy oziq-ovqat tizimlarini integratsiya qilish uchun hamjamiyatlarga katta imkoniyatlar beradi, shuning uchun u turizmning bir qismi deb hisoblaydi. bizning hayotimiz. Hozirgi kunda ko'pchilik odamlar nafaqat tabiatning ajoyib manzaralarini va dunyoning ajoyib go'zal joylarini ko'rish, balki turli oshxona oshxonalarining lablarini siqadigan taomlarini tatib ko'rish uchun sayohat qilishadi. Sir emaski, har bir oshxona o'z ta'mi va taomlari bilan bir-biridan farq qiladi va o'ziga xosdir. Oziq-ovqat turizmi, pazandalik turizmi va gastronomiya turizmi ham xuddi shunday maqsadni ko'zlaydi va ular yillar davomida rivojlangan va qo'llaridan kelganicha harakat qilishgan. Ichimliklar va oziq-ovqat odamlarning kundalik hayotining iste'mol ehtiyojlaridir. Ushbu tadqiqot, shuningdek, gastronomik markazning joylashuvi, markazi, shuningdek, uning boshlangan joyi va vaqti va gastronomik turizmga qiziqqan birinchi odam kim bo'lganini o'rganadi. Bu oshxona nafaqat mahalliy xalqimiz, balki sayyohlarga ham manzur bo'lib, o'zining o'ziga xosligi, mazali taomlari, ayniqsa, hech qayerda uchramaydigan o'zbek nonini alohida ta'kidlaydi. Bundan tashqari, ushbu tadqiqot Meksika oshxonasi, uning ta'mi va o'ziga xosligini o'rganish bo'lib, u Meksika oshxonasining ko'pchilikka nima uchun yoqishini ta'kidlaydi. Ya'ni, u Meksika oshxonasining*

o'ziga xosligini va uning ayrimlarini qamrab oladi sayyohlarga yoqadigan milliy taomlar. Afsuski, bizning mamlakatimiz Meksika bilan taqqoslaganda orqada qolmoqda, ammo bu ishda o'zbek oshxonamizni rivojlantirish yo'llari tahlil qilinadi. Odamlar globallashuv davrida yashayotgani uchun gastronomik turizmni yanada jozibador qilishning ko'plab usullari mavjud. va ko'proq sayyohlarni jalb qilish uchun O'zbekiston va Meksika oshxonalarining menyusi qanday ishlab chiqiladi, shuning uchun ushbu maqolada shu haqida tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: gastronomik turizm, milliy oshxona, labni siqadigan ovqatlar, restoranlar,

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays the popularity of culinary tourism is increasing day by days. The culinary tourism has been developing over the years, and despite the fact that people live in the 21st century and it still doesn't lose its popularity and importance. Even if gastronomy is not the main purpose of their journey, good (original, traditional, famous) food, available at the place where they are staying, often tips the scales when it comes to the choice of holiday destination (Stasiak 2007). According to Krawiak & Stasiak (2015), the majority of people interested in traveling for gastronomic motivations started to increase gradually from the birth of 21st century. Gastronomic tourism is one of the most engaging and important trends in contemporary cultural tourism. Even, during those times, when the world was not well developed, despite this fact gastronomy tourism existed and tried to do its best. Food also has become an essential part which is formed from plants, or animals to sustain human's biological needs. (Peres, 2021). With this to say, food and tourism has becoming the key aspect of people's travel experience where it is a must to taste lip-smacking foods and to have an insight about its culture. According to sustainable food scholar Michael Mikulak (2013), food is "good to think with", and the story of food is important as its physical substance. Hence, Uzbekistan has also an incredible cuisine kitchen with various flavors, but in comparison to Mexico unfortunately it is logging behind. There are some significant approaches that can develop our cuisine kitchen in order to make it on the same level with Mexico. Firstly, including different kinds of foods and making the atmosphere more pleasant can be a solution to this issue. Uzbek people can make the atmosphere at restaurants cozy and incredible. The design of restaurants and cafes can be developed by adding various patterns and bright colors. Secondly, it is significant to maintain hygiene and cleanliness in the restaurants and Uzbek kitchens. It is pleasant for everyone to dine out in the tidy venues. Thirdly, the employees must be well trained for excellent service. That is to say, they must be polite, kind with customers, and must learn to bring the order in time, because a great many of people don't have patience to wait a lot for their order. Besides it, Uzbek people can make the menu perfect by adding scrumptious foods and flavors not only Uzbek but also others. Additionally, there must be free wi-fi, and probably a little corner full of books, so people won't feel themselves bored. Psychologically speaking, people usually opt for the venues where the atmosphere is mondo-fabulous, that is to say due to pleasant atmosphere they can attract not only local people, but also tourists. Moreover, waiters and waitresses must be responsive, they must be always ready to lend a helping hand and deal with customer's complaints and concerns. Besides it, a great attention should be paid to the music that is usually played in our cuisine kitchens and so on. Metaphysically speaking, music is the best remedy for awakening the soul and psychologically it is proved that it can relieve stress and alleviate symptoms of depression. Nonetheless, there are some restaurants and cafes that cost and arm and a leg. That is to say, the cost of restaurants must be average, so that it can be affordable not only for local people, but also for tourists. Last but not least, ensure order accuracy must be

perfect. That is to say, waiters and waitresses need to be punctual and make sure that orders are correct. This essay will explore about the development and importance of gastronomy tourism.

Furthermore, tourism can create an incredible effect in economic sector, where the tourists find some leisure time spending activities of growing of food and beverage industry has shown the increase of food, especially during travelling. According to Krawiak & Stasiak(2015), It was actually Lopes who started to take an engaging interest in the issues of nutrition and cooking, as well as travelling in search of new tastes. Afterwards, the gastronomic tourism began to spread all over the world and developed as quickly as possible. According to Maengkom the term culinary comes from the Greek word *culinarius* which is related to cook and *culina* kitchen. As the first layer of Maslow hierarchy of needs, primary motivation of people to eat is in order to fulfil the needs to satisfy the hunger(2022, as cited in Putra, 2021). Culinary has been recognized identically with consuming the type of food and beverage (Ketaren, 2021). At the birth of 21st century a great many of people, after Lopes got interested in culinary tourism, and began to try it. Nonetheless, despite the fact that the world was not well developed and it was not the time of Era globalization, it was a great opportunity for them to travel and taste different kinds of scrumptious foods. Moreover, this kind of travel inspired the majority of people. That is to say, tourists can taste the foods, but besides it they can develop and take part in culinary events, meet chefs, and also try to cook something lip-smacking. Furthermore, in modern life culinary business tourism plays a crucial role. The majority of people tend to visit local festivals in order to experience different kinds of flavors, beverages and foods. It is not a secret that by experiencing various flavors, and foods they will also get a great insight about types of foods and its culture.

Moreover, Uzbek kitchen is adored not only by local people, but also by tourists, especially most of them adore our national food which is called plov. Nonetheless, the Uzbek people are proud of their cuisine kitchen, and the peculiarity of the Uzbek people considers to be a food. For ages, our country has been proud of its lip-smacking cuisine kitchen that includes appetizing foods with various flavors. The common foods that are liked by a great many of tourists are: plov, manti, bichak, somsa and others. Especially these foods touch the core of tourists hearts, because only Uzbek people are the masters of these foods, and their cooking differs a lot from others. Besides it, a significant feature of Uzbek kitchen considers to be bread, which is cooked in a special oven that is called tandir. One more puff bread that Uzbek people make usually from puff pustry called fatir. In addition to it, the food of restaurants and cafes has been developing in a highly competitive environment in the tourism sector. Therefore, one of the Republics which considered to have an activity influencing development economic and social seems to be Mexico. According to Cuevas, tourism diversifies and energizes destinations in this sense in the Mexican Republic it is considered an activity influencing development economic and social. Among the centers most visited by tourists are the colonial cities rich in cultural heritage as cited in (Cuevas, 2017). Mexico's kitchen considers to be mondo-fabulous and its food is lip-smacking. That is why the majority of people visit this country in order to taste its scrumptious foods. From this perspective, tourism currently requires strategic planning oriented in the long term, with emphasis on improving the operation of development pf companies dedicated to serving the visitor ,as is the case of gastronomic business or restaurants. Mexico is an important destination with anthropological, natural, and cultural attractions; therefore, gastronomic tourism is an essential part of the local life of the inhabitants of the country (Lopez, 2016 & Prieto, 2019 as cited in Correa Garcia). However, our Uzbek kitchen is not bad compared to Mexico. Our cuisine kitchen is liked by a great many of people from various countries. Despite national foods, Uzbek people can add

more various foods from other cultures, in order to make our Uzbek kitchen more engaging and amazing. Mexico's kitchen is developing day by days, and it is liked by a great many of people. That is to say, that is why the majority of people opt for Mexico, in order to taste its scrumptious foods, while Uzbekistan kitchen is also leading by its national foods like pilav, mantu, somsa and others. Furthermore, Mexico's kitchen has lots of various appetizing flavors, so it is huge because of its flavors, and probably that's why Mexico's kitchen is adored by a great many of people. The famous species that are liked by a great many of people are :anise, avocado leaves, garlic, epazote, coriander, marjoram, bay leaf, achoite and others.

CONCLUSION

To sum up, there are two sides of the same coin. From the first side of a coin, it is clear that gastronomic tourism plays a great role in our lives, therefore tourism industry would not be developed without it and it would see mind-numbing without this type of tourism. But, from another side it is obvious that there are lots of various ways how to broaden gastronomic tourism and make it more engaging. People live in the era of globalization, that is to say the world has lots of opportunities to develop gastronomic tourism and make the menu of various kitchens more lip smacking and engaging. Therefore, it will never be out of fashion and it will never be considered to be as outdated type of tourism.

REFERENCES

1. Jakulski. (2015). Gastronomy as a tourism Attraction for Lodz. *Tourism, 0007*.
<https://doi.org/10.1515>
2. Ketaren, I. (2021). Literature Review of Food Tourism, Culinary Tourism and Gastronomy Tourism. *Innovation Research and Knowledge, 1(4)*.
3. Peres. (2021). Literature review of food tourism, culinary tourism and Gastronomy tourism. *Innovation Research and Writing , 1(4)*.
4. Putra, A. N. (2021). Literature Review of Food Tourism, Culinary Tourism and Gastronomy Tourism. *Innovation Research and Knowledge, 1(4)*.
5. Stasiak, A. (2015). .Gastronomy As a Tourism Attraction for Lodz. *Tourism, 0007*.
<https://doi.org/10.1515>
6. Lopez, & Prieto. (2019). Literature Review of Food Tourism, Culinary Tourism and Gastronomy Tourism, *Innovation Research and Writing, 1(4)*.